

Improving Building Energy Consumption Predictions Using Machine Learning Methods

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Abstract

Energy efficiency is critical in the sustainable development of cities and countries alike. Data-driven techniques can provide flexible and efficient mechanisms for scalable methods for the integration of smart infrastructure. Machine Learning (ML) approaches are important since their modelling capabilities provide an excellent means to derive high-level correlations as well as classify and predict energy consumption. This work compares different ML models to improve the prediction of energy consumption using fine grained energy usage data in residential buildings in France. Comparisons are made using performance measures including the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and coefficient of determination (R²). A tree-based Light GBM is found to be the most optimal and key features in the data are discussed and implemented to improve model accuracy for energy consumption predictions.

Key Words: Machine learning, Energy consumption prediction, Sustainability, Feature engineering, Light GBM, WiDS 2022

1. Introduction

Energy consumption in buildings, both residential and commercial, account for more than 50% of global electricity and 40% carbon dioxide emissions worldwide¹. Climate Change Acts, such as The Paris Agreement, provide the global targets to combat climate change. Energy-efficient buildings provide a cost-effective strategy for climate change mitigation via decarbonization. While traditional methods to predict energy consumption in buildings exist, improving these approaches is essential. The use of Machine Learning (ML) models provides efficient mechanisms to achieve predictive results quickly. However, various aspects of features concerning the data collected and incorporated into the modelling process need to be reviewed for more accurate energy consumption predictions.

¹ Allouhi, A., El Fouih, Y., Kousksou, T., Jamil, A., Zeraoui, Y., and Y. Mourad. (2015). "Energy consumption and efficiency in buildings: current status and future trends," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 109, 118–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.05.139>

Zhao et al. (2018) stated that occupants have a greater impact on the energy consumption in residential buildings than in other types of buildings². As such, the features that have an impact on energy consumption in residential buildings should be carefully collected and accurately measured to enhance their predictive performance. Zhao et al. (2018) also indicates that a comprehensive understanding of the features affecting home energy consumption is lacking, without which it is less likely to develop effective energy efficiency programs and provide relevant educational information to occupants.

In addition to this, lack of data availability and standardized metrics are significant limitations to accurate building energy consumption prediction. In this way, extraction of features from the available data can improve the data analysis process challenges of redundant and unrelated information clouding the features, which may undermine the performance of the currently used ML-based methods³.

Currently, few research papers have investigated the impact of feature selection on building energy consumption prediction, particularly in residential buildings. Ahmad et al. (2014) used ML techniques such as support vector and artificial neural networks to predict building electrical energy usage⁴ while Amasyali and El-Gohary (2018) investigated features of the data and pre-processing methods, as well as ML prediction algorithms and evaluation performance measures⁵. Also, Wei et al. (2018) reviewed and discussed existing applications of building energy analyses for various archetypes, and granularities, indicating that data-driven approaches can be integrated into prediction of energy specific demand⁶.

Using these ideas to support this emerging area, the purpose of the work presented in this study is to provide the most optimal building energy consumption prediction using ML. This evidently opens the discussion about key aspects of feature selection and insights to improve the accuracy of the models. A case is made using a data set derived from fine grained building gas consumption data across regions in France. Features inherent in building input parameters can influence the accuracy of ML prediction methods.

The work presented in this paper attempts to provide some insights on energy consumption prediction by evaluating several prediction algorithms, including ordinary least squares

² Zhao, D., McCoy, A. P., Agee, P., Mo, Y., Reichard, G., and F. Paige, (2018). "Time effects of green buildings on energy use for low-income households: A longitudinal study in the United States," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 40, 559–568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2018.05.011>

³ Qiao, Q., Yunusa-Kaltungo, A., and Edwards, R. E. (2020). "Towards developing a systematic knowledge trend for building energy consumption prediction," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 35, 101967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2020.101967>

⁴ Ahmad, A. S., Hassan, M. Y., Abdullah, M. P., Rahman, H. A., Hussin, F., Abdullah H., and Saidur, R. (2014). "A review on applications of ANN and SVM for building electrical energy consumption forecasting," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 33, 102–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.01.069>

⁵ Amasyali K., and El-Gohary, N. M. (2018). "A review of data-driven building energy consumption prediction studies," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 81, 1192–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.04.095>

⁶ Wei, Y., Zhang, X., Shi, Y., Xia, L., Pan, S., Wu, J., Han, M., and Zhao, X. (2018) "A review of data-driven approaches for prediction and classification of building energy consumption," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, 1027–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.108>

regression, support vector regression, Decision Trees, Gradient Boosted Trees and Light GBM. Insights into the attributes of the data set are also discussed using feature engineering.

The two main research questions are:

1. What is the most optimal ML model for building energy consumption in France?
2. Can features be further improved or transformed to improve model accuracy?

The overall purpose of this work is to provide a framework to assist in the identification of general features of importance when conducting building energy usage forecasting/prediction and discuss opportunities to enhance the accuracy and robustness of prediction outcomes. This would be key in providing guidance for future work in this field. The criticality of stable and reliable energy can never be overemphasized, which is perhaps why policymakers and governments across the world are continuously implementing regulations, policies and in some cases incentives that are aimed at promoting building energy saving initiatives (Qiao, Yunusa-Kaltungo & Edwards, 2020).

2. Related Works

2.1 Modelling Energy Consumption Across Buildings

While existing building energy consumption prediction approaches have significantly enhanced energy forecasting, the ever-increasing complexity of the energy systems associated with modern day buildings have made it imperative to seek smarter and more reliable approaches (Qiao, Yunusa-Kaltungo & Edwards, 2020). Factors affecting building energy consumption include variations in occupant behaviour relating to use of household appliances, as well as age, function and geographical location of buildings. However, in many cases such data is limited or inaccurate due to poor data collection mechanisms using traditional approaches. Therefore, data-driven ML models have been an essential complement to traditional ones for more accurate models and insights.

ML methods are widely studied and applied in the prediction of building energy consumption. Since the factors associated with building energy behaviors are quite abundant and complex the selection of subsets of features influenced the model performance when the statistical learning method is adopted to derive the model. Optimal features were selected on two criteria: feasibility to obtain them and the scores they provided under the evaluation. They reported that the proposed feature selection method gave prediction accuracy and reduced computational time.

2.2 Prediction and Classification Approaches

Firstly Wei et al. (2018) provided a review of prediction and classification approaches for building energy consumption indicating four basic themes: physical, statistical, artificial intelligence (AI) and hybrid methods. In particular, data-driven methods are fundamentally grouped into statistical and AI method. Statistical methods which mechanically seek to establish the input-output data relationships, and AI methods apply self-learning, self-adjusting and generalization abilities to achieve similar outcomes more efficiently initiatives (Qiao, Yunusa-Kaltungo & Edwards, 2020).

ML techniques which fall under the purview of AI, are essential to the modelling process and the main approaches used are supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

Recently, a review of ML Techniques in several studies reported on prediction models for building energy usage using data-driven methods. For instance, Bourdeau et al. (2019) reviewed building

energy consumption modeling, forecasting techniques and data-driven methods⁷. The review of the work in this area outlined the most popular techniques, such as Autoregressive models (AR), statistical regressions, k-nearest neighbors (k-NN), decision trees (DT), support vector machine (SVM) and artificial neural networks (ANN).

These techniques implemented were also reviewed in the contexts of the input data characteristics (data type, granularity, amount) and data pre-processing methods, building typologies, targeted energy end-uses, forecasting horizons, accuracy assessment, and the modeling tools or software used. Since the dataset for France contains similar data types as that research, the aforementioned ML models are also applied in our research to choose the best performing one for the dataset.

Subsequently, while Bourdeau et al. (2019) acknowledged many research papers and methodologies, the researchers also indicated that several aspects still require particular attention, such as long-term energy consumption forecasting, black-box data-driven techniques, the accurate and realistic accounting for occupancy and occupants' behavior and real use cases of residential or mixed-use buildings.

Following this, Ibrahim et al. (2022) supported the use of Statistical and ML tools as a means of accurately quantifying the energy performance of residential buildings⁸. Eight different design parameters of a typical house in the Qassim region were used to generate the energy data to predict energy consumption including Building Size, Floor Height, Glazing Area, Wall Area, window to wall ratio. Multiple linear regression (MLR) and Multilayer perceptron (MLP) methods were used and the results compared using the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and coefficient of determination (R²) performance measures. These measures are also applied in our research to assess the performance of the ML models.

2.3 Deep Learning Techniques

Deep Learning techniques have also been applied to building energy consumption in France. Research in del Real, Dorado and Durán (2020) predicted energy demand for the French Grid using feature extraction capabilities from a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and regression capabilities from an Artificial Neural Network (ANN)⁹. This combination took advantage of the benefits of both neural networks and the results outperformed the existing RTE, French based subscription service. This proved that deep learning techniques can achieve more accurate forecasting.

Subsequently, several studies predicted building future energy consumption based on historical data. Other research analyzed Deep Learning with Time series analysis as supported by available energy consumption data. The research in Lara- Benítez, Carranza-García and Riquelme (2021) reviewed the use of deep learning techniques for time series forecasting in recent years¹⁰. They extensively explored applications of several deep learning architectures such as convolutional neural networks (CNN), multilayer perceptron (MLP), recurrent neural network (RNN), long-short

⁷ Bourdeau, M., qiang Zhai, X., Nefzaoui, E., Guo, X., and Chatellier, P. (2019). "Modeling and forecasting building energy consumption: A review of data-driven techniques," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 48, 101533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2019.101533>

⁸ Ibrahim, D. M., Almhafdy, A., Al-Shargabi, A. A., Alghieth, M., Elragi, A., and Chiclana, F. (2022). "The use of statistical and machine learning tools to accurately quantify the energy performance of residential buildings," *PeerJ Computer Science*, 8, e856. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.856>

⁹ del Real, A. J., Dorado, F., and Durán, J. (2020). "Energy Demand Forecasting Using Deep Learning: Applications for the French Grid," *Energies*, 13(9), 2242. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13092242>

¹⁰ Lara-Benítez, P., Carranza-García, M., and Riquelme, J. C. (2021). "An Experimental Review on Deep Learning Architectures for Time Series Forecasting," *International Journal of Neural Systems*, 31(3), 2130001. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0129065721300011>

term memory (LSTM) and gated recurrent unit (GRU). These models were robust for the related energy consumption predictions.

Similar work was done by Slowik and Urban (2022) to forecast short-term (0 to 4 hours) energy demand for micro grids in a manufacturing plant using long short-term memory (LSTM)¹¹. The developed model was compared to convolutional neural networks (CNN). In addition, Khan et al. (2021) implemented a different approach using time series analysis by investigating the factors such as population, tourists, climatic conditions and holidays, that cause the difference between actual and forecasted energy consumption using error curve training and a hybrid model¹². The focus of the study was to help identify policymakers and smart grid operators to adjust load balance according to different factors.

2.4 Towards Building Energy Models

Altogether, these ideas set the framework for Urban Building Energy Models (UBEMs) which provide simplified information on the energy use of all buildings across a city and include features such as the location, geometries, and various other attributes of interest like building footprint, usage, material, roof type, immediate surroundings etc¹³. These provide the key attributes to predict energy consumption from such features. With the use of ML, UBEMs are expected to become fundamental tools for urban planners to assist in creating policies to support energy efficiency and more sustainable cities. Thus, the merits of associated available theoretical and empirical approaches provide the first step towards achieving these goals.

3. Methods

This study investigates the various combinations of the building characteristic variables from the WiDS 2022 Research Challenge Track - Climate Change AI: Fine grained building energy usage data as inputs to the ML Models for prediction of energy consumption.

3.1 Data Extraction

The dataset contains approximately 50,000 observations based on residential building level gas consumption across France 2019. Only residential multi-family buildings were selected and individual building footprints, attributes and relevant local weather data were collected and merged using three datasets from various sources including:

- (1) building level gas use data are provided by the Ministry of the Ecological Transition and originates from the energy utility GRDF (Gaz réseau distribution France),
- (2) The building stock data, including geometries and attributes, originate from the data

¹¹ Slowik, M., and Urban, W. (2022). "Machine Learning Short-Term Energy Consumption Forecasting for Microgrids in a Manufacturing Plant," *Energies*, 15(9), 3382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15093382>

¹² Khan, P. W., Kim, Y., Byun, Y-C., and Lee, S-J. (2021). "Influencing Factors Evaluation of Machine Learning-Based Energy Consumption Prediction," *Energies*, 14(21), 7167. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14217167>

¹³ Rolnick D., Donti, P. L., Haack, L. H., Kockankasi, K., Lacoste, A., Sankaran, K., Ross, A. S., Milojevic-Dupont, N., Jaques, N., Waldman-Brown, A., Luccioni, A. S., Maharaj, T., Sherwin, E. D., Mukkavilli, S. K., Kording, K. P., Gomes, C. P., Ng, A., Hassabis, D., Platt, J. C., Creutzig, F., Chayes, J., and Bengio, Y., (2023). "Tackling Climate Change with Machine Learning," *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(2), 1-96. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3485128>

product BDTOPO by the French National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information (IGN) and

- (3) The weather data is from the dataset E-OBS from ECA&D, which comes as an ensemble dataset and is available on 0.1 regular grid. The ensemble dataset is constructed through a conditional simulation procedure.

3.2 Data Ingestion

During the data ingestion phase, the features are transformed into numerical features without missing values to be ingestible by the Machine Learning algorithm. Table 1 summarizes the processing applied to each of them.

Table 1: Variable Types

<i>Feature Name</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Processing</i>
since_age_parsed_days	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
alt_prec	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
address	Rejected	Category	
qq_dict	Input	Category	Dummy encoding
consumption	Target	Numeric	
type	Input	Category	Dummy encoding
coords_eobs	Input	Category	Dummy encoding
delivery_points	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
city_name	Input	Category	Dummy encoding
floors	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
roof_mat	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
wall_mat	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
geometry	Input	Category	Dummy encoding
id	Input	Category	Dummy encoding
height	Input	Numeric	Avg-std rescaling
age_parsed	Rejected	Numeric	

Thus, the main areas of focus included:

- Data Imputation for missing data
- Feature engineering including feature creation and feature enhancement and
- Dealing with anomalies and outliers with error analysis

3.3 Model Building

The dataset was trained and compared across eleven different regression methods including Linear, Decision Forest, Boosted decision trees, Gradient Descent and Neural Network. The target variable which is labelled as energy consumption and the other variables were then used to fit the modelled to obtain the optimal R^2 value.

From modelling the testing data, the RMSE, and R^2 statistics of several models in predicting energy consumption are shown in Table 2. There were no significant differences across the eight MLP models. The range for the values for R^2 were between 0.239 and 0.438 while the corresponding ranges for the RMSE were between 39.298 and 45.719.

While the values for R^2 were considerably small, this is more so an artifact of the dataset. Further expansion of the data set to include time series data and other related building attributes can potentially increase the performance metric.

Table 2: Model Performance based on R^2 and RMSE

<i>Model</i>	R^2	<i>RMSE</i>
Ridge Regression	0.288	44.224
Ordinary Least Squares	0.288	44.216
Gradient Boosted Trees	0.315	43.360
Light GBM	0.438	39.298
Decision Tree	0.239	45.719
Stochastic Gradient Descent	0.290	44.154
K-Nearest Neighbours	0.415	40.087
Support Vector Machine	0.328	42.961
Artificial Neural Network	0.416	40.062
LASSO-LARS	0.246	45.517
Extra Trees	0.277	44.572

The Light GBM algorithm was selected for further improvement as it performed the best in this case (Table 2). The evaluation metric used to tune the hyperparameters was R^2 Score computed on the validation dataset. After the best hyperparameter combination was found, the same metric was also computed on the test dataset. The final value was 0.438. The most proximate models

in terms of performance were the K-Nearest Neighbours and the Artificial Neural Network. These both may have underperformed due to the dataset sizes. These algorithms generally perform better when there is more data to learn from and as such may be viable contenders for bigger datasets or even real-time dataprocessing.

Regardless of data records, the Light GBM splits the tree leaf-wise as opposed to other boosting algorithms that grow tree level-wise. It chooses the leaf with maximum delta loss to grow. Since the leaf is fixed, the leaf-wise algorithm has lower loss compared to the level-wise algorithm. Leaf-wise tree growth might increase the complexity of the model and may lead to overfitting in small datasets.

This tends to work well in real world applications since energy consumptions over time can be modelled which the LightGBM model is equipped to handle based on its tree-wise growth versus level-wise growth since at each new leaf it tries to minimize loss. This can be thought of as regardless of the splitting point, the actual distribution of the samples remains the same regarding the target variable making it very robust compared to other models such as ANN.

After initial model building, some feature engineering was performed to ensure optimal model-fitting and thus improve results on the top performing model, for instance, the variable “age” was parsed and from that, the number of years relative to this year was calculated as a variable, called “since_age_parsed_years”.

Table 3: Comparison Between 1st and 2nd Modelling Iteration

<i>Model</i>	R^2	<i>RSME</i>
Light GBM (pre-feature engineering)	0.438	39.298
Light GBM (post-feature engineering - 1 st iteration)	0.464	38.375
Light GBM (post-feature engineering – 2 nd iteration)	0.52	36.035

The train and test time for the Light GBM model was very efficient, taking about 200 seconds to run across a 5-fold validation. This indicated that adding more observations enabled the model performance to improve and thus it scaled very well.

Figure 1: Model iterative performance over time for Light GBM

The model was also recomputed using both pairwise linear and pairwise polynomial combinations to explore more combinations of features. The results in Table 3 increased from 0.438 in the first run (in under a minute) to around 0.52 (in about 2 hours), as shown in Figure 1. This goes to show adding more features whilst improving model performance from the R^2 perspective also costs more time.

4. Discussion

From the overall feature engineering and modelling aspects, it was clear that often, the data itself can be improved to a point to give better results. In the first run of the model, the best performing model, which was the Light GBM model produced a R^2 of 0.438 to its final run with the parameter improvement yielding a R^2 of 0.583. This is a model performance improvement of 33% and there are ways it could have been improved such as feature engineering improvement to the other key variables.

Throughout the modelling process, the main areas identified for error improvement were in the cities where, count of cities with less data led to a bias problem where they would be underfit. To counter this in future work either more data can be collected in those cities or perhaps imploring methods to create synthetic data for imbalance data problems, where one of the simplest approaches involves duplicating examples in the minority class.

Although these examples do not add any new information to the model. Instead, new examples can be synthesized from the existing examples. Another area for error improvement would be to identify the main anomalous factors through clustering to determine appropriate thresholds instead of arbitrary ones like what was put forward in the final iteration of age over 100 years. This could have been done more precisely and is a recommendation for future work. The ability to deal with outliers more accurately, helps to better understand what works under normal circumstances and thus help to model better by reducing variability.

The combination of algorithmic flexibility and the use of Auto ML tooling allows for greater scalability and was quite effective in terms of how quickly multiple models were allowed to be trained and run times. A more detailed look at this can be explored in future work to provide more insight into scalability but preliminary work shown in this paper has been quite positive.

Another key area worth discussing is the Light GBM model itself. The Light GBM model as mentioned previously is a fast, distributed, high-performance gradient boosting framework supported decision tree algorithm, used for ranking, classification and other machine learning tasks such as index splitting. Light GBM use histogram-based algorithm, which creates buckets of continuous feature values and places them into discrete bins which fasten the training procedure. It also replaces continuous values to discrete bins which end in lower memory usage.

It produces far more complex trees by following a leaf-wise split approach instead of a level-wise approach which is the main thing about achieving higher accuracy. However, it can sometimes cause overfitting which may be avoided by setting the tuning the “maximum depth” parameter. In our case of predicting “energy consumption”, it would take all the input variables that had continuous values such as “building age” and place them into discrete bins and perform splits into each new bucket thus improving the accuracy and processing time.

Leaf-wise may cause overfitting when the data is small and although in our case there were, which was still adjusted by including the `max_depth` parameter to limit tree depth. However, trees still grow leaf-wise even when `max_depth` is specified. These combined reasons allowed us to create a highly explainable model from a feature variability standpoint using the R^2 metric.

5. Conclusions

The prediction of energy consumption has a wide spread of applications such as energy scheduling and optimization of buildings. Our current study focuses on feature engineering to improve model performance to build more robust prediction models for energy consumption in buildings. A potential real-time use of this work is contribution to policy reform in urban planning to retrofit residential buildings to facilitate eco-friendly attributes for climate action, as well as significant savings in energy and economic costs.

Some further considerations for feature selection include using buildings within a certain age range, for instance, more than 100 years old, should be eliminated from study or upgraded with proper retrofitting for more useful data aligned with updated building codes and standards.

This is a valuable stepping stone to provide improved building energy management systems (BEMS) with more standardized building energy consumption data formats to enhance prediction using machine learning (ML) algorithms. On a larger scale, in addition to informing Energy Management and Energy Efficiency, this has positive impacts in areas such as Urban Planning and thus forming more sound climate policies for residential buildings based on specific subsets of features.

Future research would examine the results of the proposed system and expand the data sets to include geographic and time series data, as well as expanding the types of buildings to commercial ones as well. It would also be useful to implement deep learning techniques for more robust models. An investigation of the effects of external variables such as socio-demographics from surveys based on occupant behaviours may also be included. One of the possible alternatives is a detailed exploration into the cities in France and other countries to create more sustainable, energy efficient cities as part of a larger framework for Smart Cities worldwide.

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¹⁴ Kaggle, Excellence in Research Award (Phase II): WiDS Datathon Further Examines the Impacts of ClimateChange (2022). <https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/phase-ii-widsdatathon2022/data>.

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